

Gendering the Study of State Authority in the MENA Region: The Case of Tunisia

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In the context of the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) where authoritarian regimes remain the norm, the question of the relationship between democratic backsliding and gender equality is far from straightforward. Important scholarly work by feminist political scientists who work on the MENA region has demonstrated the various ways in which gender relations, at large, were politicized—whether as part of broader nationalist projects of state modernization (Charrad 2000; Brand 1998) or as part of autocratic regimes' bid to seek domestic legitimacy, weaken their Islamic opponents, and increase their international legitimacy (Tripp 2019; Bush 2011). Yet, and as most of the literature shows, democracy and gender equality do not necessarily always go hand in hand. On one hand, dictators wishing to appear democratic often adopt cosmetic gender-equality measures. Such top-down policies can be utilized by active women's rights movements to push states to adopt more rights, as Tripp (2019) shows using cases from the Magherb. On the other hand, internal political contestation between incumbent authoritarian regimes and their opponents during democratic transitions can surprisingly result in the opening of political spaces for organized action on women's rights. This happened in the case of Tunisia

during the political transition between 2011 and 2017, where an active women's rights movement successfully managed to recast pre-transition legacies of state feminism in two feminist campaigns (Charrad and Zarrugh 2013). The campaigns culminated in a constitutional gender parity clause in the 2014 constitution, and a comprehensive legal code to combat all forms of violence against women in 2017.

But beyond outcome-based empirical research, how could employing a gender lens help us understand democratic backsliding in the MENA region? In my opinion, rather than focusing solely on gender outcomes, it may be more useful to theoretically rethink state power and sovereignty in gendered terms. This requires careful process tracing through a historical analysis of the often-overlooked ways in which contestations around gender contribute to the reconfiguration of state domestic sovereignty and authority, which in turn leads to democratic backsliding or the persistence of authoritarianism. Such analysis necessitates investigating how debates around gender relations reinforce the state's domestic power whereby authoritarian regimes use the agenda of women's rights to consolidate their rule.

Tunisia represents a good case to explore these dynamics. On the one hand, Tunisia is the only state that emerged as a functioning democracy following the Arab Spring, up until President Kais Saïd's constitutional coup of 2021, making it a good case to empirically investigate how and why democratic backsliding happens in general. Furthermore, state-sponsored feminism continued to play a major political role in the period following the revolution as women's rights were seen as the pinnacle of the state's modernization project. Feminist scholarly literature on Tunisia have demonstrated the various contradictions inherent in top-down state-sponsored feminist projects, including but not limited to, their effects on women's rights movements, and on ordinary women alike (Marzouki 1993; Brand 1998). The centrality of Tunisia's 1956 Personal Status Code (PSC) in the legal and constitutional history of post-colonial Tunisia points to the close links between women's rights and the legitimacy of the political regime. These links made it much easier for women's rights activists to exploit the historical legacy of state feminism when they sought more rights following the 2011 Jasmine Revolution.

But state-sponsored feminism in Tunisia had a much darker side. Over the long *durée*, state-sponsored feminism became implicated in producing local notions and practices of state sovereignty. Despite the success of the two above mentioned feminist campaigns in 2014 and 2017 and the movement's popular demands for security reforms and accountability, feminist claims contributed to the strengthening of the state's executive power. In post-revolutionary Tunisia, feminist legal campaigns for rights achieved substantial legal gains for women. However, they also, unintentionally, reconfigured state sovereignty by perpetuating the Tunisian state's prerog-

ative powers over its citizens through appealing to the logic of a protective, punitive, and interventionist state. Feminist activists sought to reconcile two competing goals: reforming the police state and curbing its power—through popular demands for justice against individual security and police officers—and protecting women—which required more state and police intervention. While such a law-centered approach to gender justice enabled feminists to achieve significant formal gains for women, it also resulted in them playing a central, albeit unintended, role in reconsolidating state authority and granting impunity to police and security agents following the democratic transition.

Analyzing state domestic sovereignty through a feminist lens helps us explain democratic backsliding in new inductive ways. On one hand, it shows how gender relations and women's rights can become a central focus for states trying to strengthen their control and legitimacy after major political changes, like the Arab uprisings. On the other hand, by appealing to the state's punitive and interventionist policies, feminists could inadvertently contribute to making gender issues a means for the state to consolidate its power and stability during times of political upheaval. ♦

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